

NATURAL FLAVONES. PART II. ON THE COLOURING MATTERS OF THE BARK OF OROXYLUM INDICUM, VENT.

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Oroxylin, the yellow colouring matter of the bark of *Oroxylum indicum*, Vent. was isolated and investigated by Naylor and his collaborators, who ascribed the formula $C_{19}H_{14}O_6$ to the compound. The present authors have been able to prove that Naylor's oroxylin is a mixture of at least three hydroxyflavones, namely, baicalein, 6-methyl-baicalein and chrysin. Chrysin and baicalein have been isolated and identified, but 6-methylbaicalein could not be completely freed from chrysin.

Oroxylum indicum, Vent. (N. O. *Bignoniaceae*; Sanskrit: Syonaka, Bengali: Sóná) has some repute in Hindu medicine (*vide* Kirtikar and Basu, "Indian Medicinal Plants", Ed. 1918, Vol. II, 940). Holmes (*Pharm. J.*, 1890-91, 21, 257) reported that the bark 'had been found by Dr. Evers to possess definite therapeutic action' in acute rheumatism. It has been reported in *Agricultural Ledger* (No. 6 of 1898) that the seeds can be used against a kind of ring-worm in cattle caused by *Tricophyton tonsurans*. Naylor and Chaplin (*Pharm. J.*, 1890-91, 21, 257) isolated a yellow crystalline substance, m.p. 228.5-229° from the bark which they called oroxylin. Werner (*Diss.* Erlangen, 1896) appears to have found the same substance in the seeds. Naylor and Dyer (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1901, 79, 954) obtained an yield of 0.2% of the product from the bark (m.p. ca. 225°) and assigned to it the formula, $C_{19}H_{14}O_6$. Some products of degradation, e.g., benzoic acid, benzaldehyde, phloroglucinol and phthalic acid were also described without proper identification except in the case of the first named substance.

By the process described in the experimental sequel we have isolated the crude colouring matter in an yield of 2.8% and from it about 1.5% of the purified product. Repeated crystallisation of the crude product gave samples having the melting point range of 220°-232° but responding to the tests ascribed to oroxylin by Naylor and Chaplin. From the crude extract, after many trials, we were able to isolate one of the components as the lead salt from an alcoholic solution of the crude extract acidified with acetic acid (*vide* Experimental). The substance, m. p. 262-65°, (brown prisms) was obtained in an yield of 0.5% of the bark used. Besides giving the colour reactions of oroxylin, it gave a voluminous greenish brown precipitate with

chloropentamine cobaltchloride indicating the presence of two -OH groups in *ortho* or *para* positions to one another (*cf.* Shibata and Hattori, *Acta Phytchim.*, 1930, 5, 117). Sodium amalgam produced an immediate green precipitate in the alcoholic solution of the substance. Hence it has three contiguous hydroxyl groups in the molecule (*cf.* Bargellini, *Gazzetta*, 1919, 49, 47). The substance was free of methoxyl and its composition agreed with $C_{15}H_{16}O_5$. Alkaline hydrolysis gave benzoic acid and acetophenone; and with diazomethane a trimethyl ether, m. p. 161° , (insoluble in dilute alkali) was formed. From these, it was concluded that the substance probably was identical with baicalein (I, $R_1=R_2=R_3=H$) (Shibata, Iwata and Nakamura, *Acta Phytchim.*, 1923, 1, 105). Prof. Shizuo Hattori very kindly sent us specimens of baicalein and its trimethyl ether with which we have established the identity of our products by direct comparison and determination of mixed m. p.

The mother-liquor, after the removal of baicalein lead salt, was treated with hydrogen sulphide, lead sulphide removed and on concentration the solution furnished bright yellow needles. This fraction will be referred to as 'oroxylol' as it did not give any of Naylor and Chaplin's tests of oroxylin. This portion after repeated crystallisation from different solvents gave a fraction which appeared uniform under the microscope but showed a range from 214° to 235° in m. p. Unlike baicalein, the mixture gave no precipitate with chloropentamine cobaltchloride and ammoniacal silver salts. Treatment of an alcoholic solution of the mixture with concentrated hydrochloric acid and magnesium produced an orange colour. Numerous attempts to separate the components of oroxylol, either by fractional precipitation of an alkaline solution or fractional crystallisation from various solvents were not successful. The mixtures obtained at various stages were, therefore, analysed and the carbon content was found to vary from 68.16 to 70.13, hydrogen from 3.96 to 4.96 and methoxyl from 6.54 to 9.76%. Therefore it seemed that the mixture might contain a fairly large percentage of a monomethyl ether of baicalein, which requires C, 67.6, H, 4.23 and OMe, 10.92%. A sample of oroxylol showing m. p. $227-230^\circ$ was demethylated and baicalein was isolated *via* its lead salt. After the separation of baicalein as its lead salt, the mother-liquor after removal of lead and concentration gave a

crop of pale yellow crystals (m. p. 274-75°) analysing for $C_{15}H_{10}O_4$. This substance was identified as chrysin by comparison with an authentic specimen kindly provided by Dr. K. Venkataraman. Hence it seems that crude oroxytol is a 6:5 mixture of a baicalein monomethyl ether and chrysin. In oroxytol, no chrysin dimethyl ether or baicalein trimethyl ether can be present owing to its complete solubility in dilute aqueous alkali. The mixture may therefore consist of—

- (i) A monomethyl baicalein (R_1 or R_2 or R_3 being Me in Formula I) + chrysin.
- (ii) A monomethyl baicalein + a monomethyl chrysin.
- (iii) A dimethyl baicalein + chrysin.
- (iv) A dimethyl baicalein + a monomethyl chrysin.

The analytical value of the mixture (m. p. 227-30°) indicates the probability of its being (i).

Of the three possible monomethyl baicaleins, the probability is of its being the 6-methyl derivative (I, $R_1 = R_3 = H$; $R_2 = Me$) as the reactions with chloropentammine cobaltichloride and *o*-dinitrobenzene (Bose, *J. Indian Chem. Soc. Sir P. C. Ray Comm. Vol.*, p. 65) point to the absence of *ortho*- or *para*-hydroxyl groups. We are engaged in synthesising 6-methyl ether of baicalein for establishing this point.

We inferred from various considerations that baicalein 6-methyl ether should have a m.p. lower than 230°. Hence some fractions with lower melting points from crude oroxytol were extracted repeatedly with chloroform and analysed. One of these, the fraction m.p. 199-200°, gave OMe less than 9 per cent, whilst a specimen, m.p. 220-223°, gave nearly the theoretical value for 6-methyl ether of baicalein. However, the amount was too small for further purification.

Recently Shah, Mehta and Wheeler (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 591; *Current Sci.*, 1935, 4, 406) have concluded that oroxylin-A (m.p. 231-32°) isolated from the root-bark of *Oroxylum indicum* is the 6-methyl ether of baicalein.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Isolation of Crude Flavones.—The bark was powdered and extracted with alcohol, and the alcohol removed from the extract under diminished pressure. This operation was carried out by Messrs. Bengal Chemical and Pharmaceutical Works, Ltd., to the authorities of which firm our best thanks are due. The residue was heated with about eight times its weight of water, cooled and filtered (Filtrate A). The residue, after being mixed with sand, was dried and then thoroughly ex-

tracted with hot benzene for 72 hours. The benzene extract was concentrated on the water-bath to a small volume, cooled and filtered. The greenish yellow crystals were washed with petroleum ether to remove adhering oil. The aqueous Filtrate A was repeatedly extracted with ether, the solvent removed and the crystalline residue washed with cold benzene and mixed with the main crude product. The total yield was 2.8% calculated on the amount of bark taken. The m.p. was indefinite (218-260°).

Isolation of Baicalein.—The crude product was dissolved in warm alcohol and filtered to remove a small quantity of insoluble matter. The clear solution was acidified with a little acetic acid, and then a concentrated aqueous solution of lead acetate was gradually added till the precipitation was complete. The dirty brick-red precipitate was filtered off and thoroughly washed with warm alcohol. It was then suspended in hot alcohol and decomposed by passing a current of sulphuretted hydrogen. After the removal of lead sulphide the filtrate, on concentration, deposited brown crystals of crude baicalein. These were purified again *via* the lead salt. Two more crystallisations from alcohol gave yellow-brown prisms, m.p. 262-65°; yield 0.5%. (Found: C, 66.79; H, 3.88. $C_{15}H_{10}O_5$ requires C, 66.66; H, 3.70 per cent). Mixed with an authentic specimen of baicalein there was no depression of m.p.

Hydrolysis of Baicalein: Isolation of Benzoic Acid and Acetophenone.—0.5 G. of baicalein was heated on the water-bath with 20 c.c. of 10% aqueous potassium hydroxide solution for 3 hours. The dark brown solution was cooled and extracted with ether (Extract a). The solution was then acidified with hydrochloric acid and again extracted with ether (Extract b). The extract (a) furnished a small quantity of an oil which gave a semicarbazone, m.p. 191-92°, undepressed on admixture with a specimen of acetophenone semicarbazone, m.p. 192-94°.

The residue from *Extract (b)* was twice sublimed in vacuum and proved to be benzoic acid by m.p. and mixed m.p.

Methylation of Baicalein.—An excess of diazomethane in ether was added to a methyl alcoholic solution of baicalein and kept overnight. The cream-coloured crystalline residue left after the removal of the solvents, was sublimed at 199-200°/0.05 mm. and then crystallised from dilute methyl alcohol, when silky needles, m.p. 160-61°, were obtained. A mixture of this substance and baicalein trimethyl ether melted at 161-62°.

Isolation of 'Oroxylol'.—The filtrates left after the separation of baicalein as the lead salt, was freed from lead by means of sulphuretted

hydrogen and the filtrate concentrated on the water-bath when bright yellow needles, m.p. 218-25°, were obtained; yield nearly 1% calculated on the air-dried bark.

Attempts to Separate the Constituents of 'Oroxylol'.

(a) *By Crystallisation.*—Repeated crystallisations from alcohol gave bright yellow needles, m.p. 227-29°. (Found : C, 79.23; H, 4.68; OMe, 7.79 per cent).

(b) *By Fractional Extraction with Chloroform.*—3 G. of 'oroxylol' were successively digested with 10 c.c. of chloroform for half an hour, cooled to room temperature and filtered.

Fraction.	(a) M.p. of residue insoluble in chloroform.	(b) M.p. of residue obtained from the filtrate.
I	218-32°	Crystals with oil
II	217-20°	173-76°
III	220-26°	"
IV	226-28°	180-81°
V	224-27°	196-98°
VI	228-30°	204-10°

There was only slight rise in m.p. after the seventh extraction of the residue insoluble in chloroform. Fraction (VIa) was analysed. (Found : C, 69.65; H, 4.29; OMe, 7.52. $C_{16}H_{12}O_6$ requires C, 67.60; H, 4.23; OMe, 10.92 per cent). 60% 6-methylbaicalein ($C_{15}H_{10}O_6$) + 40% chrysin, ($C_{15}H_{10}O_4$) requires C, 68.92; H, 4.11; OMe, 6.54 per cent.

The fractions (IIb) and (IIIb) were washed with cold benzene and then dissolved in alcohol, treated with a few drops of neutral lead acetate and filtered. The filtrate after removal of lead and concentration gave yellow prism, m.p. 222-23°. (Found : C, 68.16; H, 4.2; OMe, 9.78 per cent). Baicalein-6-methylether requires C, 67.6; H, 4.23; OMe, 10.92 per cent).

Fractions (IVb) and (Vb) were dissolved in ammonia, filtered and the filtrate fractionally precipitated with dilute hydrochloric acid. The first fraction after crystallisation from alcohol melted at 200-2° (Found : OMe, 8.74%). The second fraction after crystallisation from alcohol melted at 186-88° (Found : OMe, 8.98%). Another portion of the combined fractions (IVb) and (Vb) was sublimed at 0.025 mm. pressure and the fraction obtained below 200° collected. It melted indefinitely from 202° to 211°.

Fraction (VIa) was subjected to fractional sublimation at 0.04 mm. pressure. The product obtained at 125-200° (bath temperature) formed deep yellow needles, m.p. 219-22°. Resublimation in high vacuum gave a product which, when crystallised from dilute acetone, melted at 210-214°. The product which sublimed above 200°/0.04 mm. formed pale yellow plates

from alcohol and melted at 269-70°. Further sublimation and recrystallisation gave a substance, m.p. 273-75°, which was identified as chrysin by mixed m.p.

(c) *By Fractional Precipitation from Alkaline Solution.*—'Oroxylol' was dissolved in dilute ammonia, allowed to stand for some time and then filtered to remove a little slimy matter. The clear filtrate was treated with dilute hydrochloric acid drop by drop with constant shaking, till it became turbid. It was filtered at this stage and the turbid filtrate was treated with a little dilute hydrochloric acid and the precipitate removed. The filtrate was again treated with a small quantity of hydrochloric acid and the precipitate collected. In this way several fractions were collected; these were washed with water and dried. They were then separately crystallised from alcohol and their melting points were determined. The fractions melting within 5° of each other were mixed together and recrystallised. The major portion, after final purification, was found to melt at 233-35° (Found: C, 70.13; H, 4.63 per cent).

Hydrolysis of 'Oroxylol'.—A portion of the fraction, m.p. 228-30°, was hydrolysed with 10% alkali and the product worked up as in the case of baicalein (*vide supra*). Benzoic acid and acetophenone-semicarbazone were isolated and identified.

Demethylation of 'Oroxylol'.—A specimen (1 g.) of the fraction, m.p. 227-30°, was gently boiled with 20 c.c. of hydriodic acid (d 1.7) and enough phenol to keep the substance in solution for 2 hours. The mixture was then poured into a dilute aqueous solution of sodium sulphite. The greenish yellow precipitate was collected, washed with water, dissolved in warm alcohol and treated with an excess of lead acetate slightly acidified with acetic acid. The greenish brown precipitate was worked up for baicalein (*vide supra*), the yield of which was nearly 0.6 g. It was identified as baicalein in the usual manner.

The filtrate left after the separation of baicalein as the lead salt, was freed from lead in the usual manner and concentrated when pale yellow plates (0.35 g.) were obtained. After crystallisation from alcohol, it melted at 274-75° and did not depress the m. p. of an authentic specimen of chrysin. (Found: C, 70.85; H, 4.15. $C_{15}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 70.87; H, 3.94 per cent).

In conclusion we wish to express our thanks to Mr. Sarbakali Banerjee for some preliminary work in connexion with this investigation. Our thanks are also due to Prof. S. Hattori and Dr. K. Venkataraman for some specimens.